

COUNTING THE FEARS: UNVEILING THE STORIES OF SELF-DESCRIBED MATH-ANXIOUS STUDENTS IN A HYBRID LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

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Counting the Fears: Unveiling the Stories of Self-Described Math-Anxious Students in a Hybrid Learning Environment

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Abstract

Mathematics anxiety is a prevalent issue among college students, significantly impacting their academic performance and potential. While existing literature has extensively examined mathematics anxiety, limited studies have explored its manifestations in a hybrid learning environment particularly in the post-pandemic context. This study utilized a narrative inquiry approach to explore the lived experiences of self-identified math-anxious college students navigating hybrid learning in selected institutions across Western Visayas in the aftermath of the pandemic. The research aims to explore the dimensions of their experiences and identify emergent themes that characterize their academic struggles in hybrid learning modality. Using purposive sampling, ten self-identified math-anxious college students were selected as participants. Data were collected through online and in-person interviews using a semi-structured questionnaire. The interviews were recorded, transcribed verbatim, and analyzed using Colaizzi's method to ensure a rigorous and systematic interpretation of participants' experiences. The analysis identified key themes, including triggers of math anxiety, self-doubt, coping responses, and adaptability to the hybrid learning environment. Based on the study's findings, it is recommended that educators, institutions, and policymakers may implement targeted interventions, such as anxiety-reducing strategies, supportive environment, teacher retooling, and mental health services, to help math-anxious students succeed.

Keywords: *self-described, math anxiety, collaizzi method, hybrid learning*

Introduction

Mathematics anxiety is a common issue among students and has been known to negatively influence students' academic achievement, cognitive processes, and emotional well-being. Defined as an intense feeling of apprehension or fear when engaging in math-related tasks, math anxiety has been linked to avoidance behaviors and lower achievement in Mathematics (Bieg et al., 2022). This issue is particularly concerning in the context of a hybrid learning environment, where students must navigate both online and face-to-face instructional modes. While hybrid learning offers increased flexibility and accessibility, it also presents unique challenges that may exacerbate the struggles of math-anxious students, particularly in terms of reduced in-person support and increased self-directed learning.

Despite extensive research on math anxiety, there is still a limited understanding of how this condition manifests in hybrid learning settings. Studies have primarily focused on traditional classroom environments or fully online models, leaving a gap in knowledge about the specific experiences of students who self-identify as math-anxious in a blended learning context. With the growing adoption of hybrid education especially in response to the COVID-19 pandemic (Ndzinisa & Dlamini, 2023), it is essential to examine how this instructional format influences students' anxiety levels, engagement, and academic performance. Understanding these dynamics can help educators and policymakers design targeted interventions to support students struggling with math anxiety in hybrid settings.

This study aims to explore the lived experiences of self-described math-anxious students in a hybrid learning environment. By uncovering their challenges, coping strategies, and perceptions of hybrid education, this research seeks to provide valuable insights into how instructional practices can be improved to better accommodate students with math anxiety. Findings from this study may contribute to the development of supportive learning frameworks, inform teaching strategies, and promote inclusive education practices that foster mathematical confidence and success in diverse learning modalities.

Research Questions

Specifically, it sought answers to the following research questions:

1. What are the lived experiences of self-described Math-anxious students in a hybrid learning environment?
2. How do Math-anxious students perceive the essence of their lived experiences?
3. What coping mechanisms do self-described math-anxious students employ?

Methodology

Research Design

A qualitative narrative inquiry was employed to capture the nuanced, lived experiences of math-anxious students in a hybrid learning environment. Narrative inquiry allows researchers to explore how individuals interpret their experiences, making it suitable for examining the subjective realities of students grappling with math anxiety. A qualitative narrative inquiry was employed to capture the

nuanced, lived experiences of math-anxious students in a hybrid environment. This approach is particularly effective in understanding the personal stories and perspectives of individuals dealing with math anxiety (Cabildo et al., 2024).

Participants

Participants were purposively selected based on specific inclusion criteria. The sample consisted of undergraduate students enrolled in a hybrid mathematics course at selected state universities and colleges (SUCs) in Western Visayas, Philippines. Eligibility required participants to be officially enrolled in a state university or college in Region VI, currently enrolled in a mathematics course for the semester of participation, and aged between 18 and 22 years. Additionally, participants were required to self-identify as math-anxious and consent to participating in an interview. Individuals who self-identified as math-anxious but were not enrolled in a mathematics course during the current semester were excluded from the study. In total, 10 participants were recruited. To maintain confidentiality and protect participants' identities, pseudonyms were assigned. Participants were thoroughly informed about the purpose of the study and provided written informed consent, ensuring adherence to ethical research standards.

Table 1. Summary of Participants' Profile

Participant's Code	Age	Sex	Degree Program	Year Level
Ana	18	Male	BS in Civil Engineering	1st Year
Leo	22	Male	BS in Mechanical Engineering	1st Year
Janet	19	Female	BS in Information Technology	1st Year
Kiarra	18	Female	BS in Architecture	1st Year
Kristoff	20	Male	BS in Criminology	1st Year
Lori	19	Female	Bachelor of Secondary Education- Math	2nd Year
Mark	18	Male	BS in Architecture	1st Year
May	20	Female	Bachelor of Secondary Education- Math	2nd Year
Pablito	19	Male	BS in Civil Engineering	1st Year
Sheena	18	Female	BS in Accountancy	1st Year

Instrument

The research instrument is a semi-structured questionnaire consisting of two parts. The first part collects personal information from the self-identified math-anxious students, while the second part consists of open-ended questions designed for participant responses. To facilitate full expression of their thoughts, the questions were presented in both English and the local language. Participants were encouraged to elaborate on their answers, and researchers posed follow-up questions to encourage further clarification.

Procedure

Data were collected through comprehensive, semi-structured interviews conducted both in person and via Zoom teleconferencing, scheduled at times convenient for the participants. Preliminary analysis of the narratives was performed concurrently with data collection to assess data saturation. After interviewing the tenth participant, no new themes or significant statements emerged, indicating that data saturation had been achieved. Consequently, the sample size was deemed sufficient, aligning with the inductive thematic saturation model discussed by Yang et al. (2022). Each participant underwent two interview sessions, each lasting between 20 and 25 minutes. The initial interview aimed to establish rapport and gather basic personal information through a semi-structured format. The subsequent interview delved into the participants' lived experiences as self-described math-anxious students, guided by open-ended questions. Prior to each interview, the study's objectives were explained, and permission to audio-record the sessions was obtained. The interviews concluded with expressions of gratitude and the distribution of tokens to the participants.

Data Analysis

The study employed Colaizzi's method to systematically interpret the narratives of self-described math-anxious students, providing a structured approach to analyzing their lived experiences in a hybrid learning environment. This method ensured a rigorous and comprehensive examination of participants' accounts, allowing for the identification of key themes, patterns, and underlying meanings related to math anxiety. The transcribed interviews were coded using a predetermined scheme to extract meaningful insights. Researchers first immersed themselves in the data by thoroughly reading and rereading transcripts to understand participants' experiences. They then identified and coded significant statements, highlighting key excerpts related to math anxiety. These statements were analyzed to formulate meanings, ensuring both implicit and explicit experiences were captured. The meanings were then clustered into related themes, identifying patterns and commonalities among participants. These themes were synthesized into exhaustive descriptions to construct a fundamental structure representing the core essence of math anxiety in hybrid learning. Finally, an integrated narrative was developed, incorporating direct participant quotations to enhance validity and provide a rich, authentic interpretation of their experiences.

Ethical Considerations

As part of the ethical considerations in research involving human participants, the researchers obtained informed consent from the self-

identified math-anxious students and scheduled interviews at each participant's convenience. Prior to each interview session, whether conducted in person or via Zoom, the researchers explained the study's objectives. Participants also provided consent for the audio and video recording of the entire interview. All participants signed a free and informed consent form before the interviews began.

Results and Discussion

The results of the narrative inquiry underscored the complex and multifaceted nature of Mathematics anxiety among participants in a hybrid learning environment. The analysis revealed key themes, including Triggers of Mathematics anxiety, Self-Doubt, Coping Responses, and Learning Environment Adaptability. Triggers of Mathematics anxiety were linked to past negative experiences and uncertainty in hybrid learning, which heightened students' apprehension. Self-doubt emerged as another critical theme, characterized by a fear of making mistakes and the tendency to compare oneself to peers, further exacerbating anxiety. In response, participants employed various coping responses, such as self-taught strategies and seeking social support to manage their feelings of anxiety. Lastly, learning environment adaptability played a significant role, with students expressing a strong preference for in-person learning while struggling with online engagement. These findings highlight the intricate ways in which Mathematics anxiety manifests and how students navigate their learning experiences in a hybrid learning environment.

Table 2. Summary of Emerging Themes Using Narrative Inquiry Analysis

Themes	Sub-Themes	Narratives	Interpretation
Triggers of Math Anxiety	Prior Adverse Experiences	"I struggled with Math since high school. Every time I see numbers, I feel like I will fail again."	Previous difficulties in Math contribute to heightened anxiety in college.
	Uncertainty in Hybrid Learning	"I don't know if I'm learning enough in online classes. I feel lost and unsure during exams."	The unfamiliarity and inconsistency of hybrid learning amplify participants' feelings of anxiety.
Self-Doubt	Fear of Making Mistakes	"I hesitate to answer in class because I'm scared of being wrong."	The fear of failure discourages active participation and deepens anxiety.
	Comparison with Peers	"I see my classmates solving problems easily, and I feel like I'm not smart enough."	Comparing oneself to others lowers confidence and reinforces negative self-beliefs.
Coping Responses	Self-Taught Strategies	"I watch tutorial videos and practice on my own to understand the lessons better."	Independent learning helps participants manage their anxiety and improve competence.
	Seeking Social Support	"I always ask my friends for help. Studying together makes math less stressful."	Peer support provides emotional reassurance and practical assistance.
Learning Environment Adaptability	Preference for In-Person Learning	"I learn better when the teacher is in front of me explaining concepts."	Face-to-face instruction enhances comprehension and reduces feelings of isolation.
	Struggles with Online Engagement	"It's hard to focus during online classes. I easily get distracted and feel disconnected."	Online learning challenges participants' engagement, affecting their learning process.

Triggers of Math Anxiety

Math anxiety is a pervasive issue that affects students' confidence, academic performance, and overall engagement with mathematics. The findings of this study revealed that in a hybrid learning environment participants faced multiple triggers that intensified their anxiety. Two significant contributors that emerged were past negative experiences and uncertainty in hybrid learning. These triggers shaped participants' perceptions of their mathematical abilities and influenced their approach to learning in both online and in-person settings.

Prior Adverse Experiences

For many participants, Mathematics anxiety stemmed from prior adverse experiences with the subject. All participants recalled struggling with mathematical concepts, receiving low grades, and feeling embarrassed when making mistakes in class. "I struggled with Math since high school. Every time I see numbers, I feel like I will fail again." These experiences instilled a lasting fear of failure, causing them to associate Mathematics with frustration and a lack of motivation to learn. A common theme among participants was the impact of early academic struggles and negative reinforcement from teachers and classmates. Many described instances where educators dismissed their difficulties or offered harsh criticism, making them reluctant to engage in mathematical tasks.

This finding aligns with research suggesting that such prior experiences contribute to the development of math anxiety (Doz & Doz, 2023). In addition to these past challenges, the transition to hybrid learning introduced new stressors, with students highlighting the uncertainty of this format as a key source of stress. Specifically, they mentioned technical difficulties with online platforms and feelings of isolation, both of which exacerbated their existing math anxiety. These findings underscore the compounded nature of math anxiety in a hybrid context, where both past experiences and the challenges of new learning formats contribute to students' emotional responses. Previous studies have also shown that the shift to online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic has significantly affected students'

math anxiety levels (Garcia & Martinez, 2022).

Uncertainty in Hybrid Learning

In addition to past experiences, uncertainty in hybrid learning emerged as a key trigger for math anxiety. "I don't know if I'm learning enough in online classes. I feel lost and unsure during exams". Many participants expressed that the shift between online and face-to-face learning modes created confusion, disrupted their learning routines, and intensified their academic stress. Unlike traditional in-person classes, where they could seek immediate clarification from teachers, the online component of hybrid learning often lacked real-time feedback, making it difficult for students to address their misunderstandings.

Technical difficulties, such as unstable internet connections, unfamiliarity with digital tools, and difficulty navigating online platforms, further compounded their anxiety. Participants shared that poor connectivity during virtual lectures made it challenging to follow explanations, leading to frustration and gaps in understanding. This lack of accessibility heightened their fear of falling behind, particularly when they could not easily reach out to instructors for support. Studies indicate that inconsistent access to technological resources and inadequate digital literacy can increase academic stress, particularly among students with existing learning anxieties (Dodongan, 2022).

Self-Doubt

Self-doubt emerged as a central theme in the narratives of math-anxious students navigating a hybrid learning environment. Many participants expressed a persistent lack of confidence in their mathematical abilities, which hindered their academic performance and overall engagement in learning. This self-doubt often stemmed from past failures, negative feedback, or repeated struggles with mathematical concepts. The hybrid learning setup further intensified these insecurities, as students felt an increased pressure to independently grasp mathematical concepts without the immediate reassurance of an instructor. The participants' experiences reveal how self-doubt can create a cycle of avoidance, decreased motivation, and heightened anxiety, ultimately impacting their ability to succeed in mathematics.

Fear of Making Mistakes

One major contributor to self-doubt among students was the fear of making mistakes in Mathematics. "I hesitate to answer in class because I'm scared of being wrong". Many participants shared that they hesitated to participate in class discussions, both online and in person, due to a deep-seated fear of being judged by their peers or receiving negative feedback from instructors. This fear was particularly evident in the online learning setting, where the lack of immediate clarification led to heightened anxiety and reluctance to ask questions. Research has shown that the fear of failure is a common trait among math-anxious students, often leading to avoidance behaviors that hinder academic progress (Doz & Doz, 2023).

Comparing Oneself to Peers

Another factor contributing to self-doubt was the tendency to compare oneself to peers, which exacerbated feelings of inadequacy. "I see my classmates solving problems easily, and I feel like I'm not smart enough." Participants frequently mentioned that they felt less capable than their classmates, especially when they struggled with solving problems that others completed with ease. The hybrid learning environment, with its mix of synchronous and asynchronous activities, sometimes made these comparisons more pronounced, as students could see recorded lectures or discussion forums showcasing their peers' work. This constant comparison reinforced their belief that they were not "math-minded," making them more likely to disengage from learning opportunities (Polydoros, 2024).

Coping Response

In response to their anxiety, seven out of ten participants employed self-directed strategies to improve their understanding of mathematical concepts. These strategies included watching instructional videos and seeking support from peers. In addition, three participants reported turning to parents or relatives who were proficient in mathematics for assistance. Participants learned to develop various coping responses to manage their Mathematics anxiety and improve their performance in a hybrid learning environment. These responses are essential for navigating the challenges posed by both online and in-person learning settings, wherein they had adapted to different teaching methods, assessment formats, and levels of support. The findings of this study revealed two primary coping responses: self-taught strategies and seeking social support. These approaches reflect students' efforts to regain confidence, overcome their fears, and enhance their mathematical abilities despite their anxiety.

Self-Taught Strategies

One of the most common coping responses among math-anxious students is the use of self-taught strategies to supplement their learning. "I watch tutorial videos and practice on my own to understand the lessons better." Majority participants reported that they turned to online resources, such as instructional videos, digital tutorials, and self-paced exercises, to reinforce their understanding of mathematical concepts. Research has shown that self-regulated learning strategies, such as independent study and online tutorials, can significantly reduce academic anxiety and enhance comprehension in mathematics (Garcia & Martinez, 2023; Dodongan, 2022; Natividad, 2021).

Seeking Social Support

"I always ask my friends for help. Studying together makes math less stressful." In addition to independent learning, seeking social support emerged as another crucial coping response among math-anxious students. Some of participants relied on peer assistance, family support, and instructor guidance to navigate their difficulties with mathematics. The reliance on peer support highlights the social nature of learning and underscores the importance of collaboration in reducing feelings of isolation and anxiety, particularly in remote learning environments (Worley et al., 2023). This finding aligns with Natividad's (2021) study, which suggests that self-regulated learning can effectively mitigate math anxiety. Furthermore, Polydoros (2024) emphasized that the frequent use of peer assistance as a coping strategy reinforces the critical role of social support in managing academic stress.

Learning Environment Adaptability

Another major theme that emerged from this study is the participants' adaptability to different learning environments, which plays a crucial role in their ability to manage academic challenges related to Mathematics anxiety. The findings of this study revealed that participants struggled with adapting to the changing learning modalities, with two key subthemes emerging: preference for in-person learning and struggles with online engagement.

Preference for In-Person Learning

Several participants expressed a strong preference for in-person learning, as it provided a more structured and supportive environment. "I learn better when the teacher is in front of me explaining concepts." They felt that face-to-face instruction allowed for immediate feedback, clearer explanations, and direct interaction with both teachers and peers, which helped alleviate their anxiety. Unlike online learning, where technical limitations and feelings of isolation often made them hesitant to ask questions, in-person classes encouraged active participation and facilitated clarification. Doz and Doz (2023) highlighted that students' preference for face-to-face instruction is linked to the immediate feedback and reduced sense of isolation it offers. Research has also shown that in-person learning environments are associated with lower levels of math anxiety.

Struggles with Online Engagement

While hybrid learning introduced flexibility, all of the participants found online learning to be a source of stress and disengagement. "It's hard to focus during online classes. I easily get distracted and feel disconnected." One of the most common challenges was the lack of immediate support, which left them feeling lost when they encountered difficult mathematical concepts. Unlike in-person classes, where they could receive instant clarification, online sessions often involved delayed responses from instructors or difficulties in expressing their concerns through digital platforms. Technical issues, such as poor internet connectivity, software glitches, and unfamiliarity with digital tools, further exacerbated their anxiety. Several participants reported that interruptions in online lectures led to gaps in their understanding, making it difficult to keep up with the lessons. Participants reported difficulties in maintaining focus and engagement during online classes, which intensified their math anxiety. Bertoletti et al. (2023) and Palan (2024) highlighted that the virtual classroom setting can present unique challenges for students with Mathematics anxiety.

Conclusions

The hybrid learning environment offers both benefits and challenges for self-identified Math-anxious students. While flexibility in online classes helps some, the lack of immediate feedback often intensifies their anxiety, highlighting the importance of real-time support in hybrid learning models. The study emphasizes the need to design hybrid environments that cater to the unique needs of self-described Math-anxious students, incorporating regular feedback, interaction, and empathetic teaching approaches. Educators can reduce self-doubt and foster a supportive environment through personalized feedback, reassurance, and mindfulness techniques. To mitigate Math anxiety, instructors should provide constructive feedback, encourage collaborative problem-solving, and create a safe space for students to engage with mathematical concepts without fear of judgment. Developing coping strategies such as flexible pacing, interactive tools, and peer mentoring, along with ensuring smooth transitions between online and in-person modalities, may help students build confidence. Furthermore, training programs for educators, mental health support services, and policies prioritizing student well-being are crucial for making hybrid learning more inclusive and effective for Math-anxious students.

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